

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Microstructural Effect and FTIR Study of Co-Doped Calcium Copper Titanate ($\text{CaCu}_3\text{Ti}_4\text{O}_{12}$)

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Abstract

Objectives: To discover the influence of the Co atom by replacing the Ti atom in CCTO on its chemical properties. **Methods:** Pure and Co-doped CCTO ($\text{CaCu}_3\text{Ti}_{4-x}\text{Co}_x\text{O}_{12}$, $x=0.05, 0.10, 0.15$) ceramics synthesized via solid-state reaction and heating at 950°C for 12 hours with a heating rate of 4°C/min. X-ray Diffraction (XRD) confirmed that CCTO has a single-phase structure. Field Effect Scanning Electron Microscopy (FE-SEM) was used to examine the grain size, and Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FT-IR) was used to record the absorption band for all samples. **Findings:** The size of the material decreases by the doping of the Co atom. No change observed in the shape by the doping of Co atoms in place of Ti atoms. The average particle size of the samples is between 0.3-0.5 micrometers. **Novelty:** The bond strength improves with the doping of the Cobalt atom. A broad absorption band is observed with the peak of this band shifting towards lower wave numbers. This will be a required condition for energy storage applications. It also enhances the use of CCTO in pharmaceuticals, chemical synthesis, and environmental remediation.

Keywords: FESEM; XRD; FTIR; EDS; CCTO

1 Introduction

The demand for electronics is increasing, and energy-related problems are becoming a global issue as science and technology advance⁽¹⁾. Titanium dioxide (TiO_2), barium titanate (BaTiO_3), strontium titanate (SrTiO_3), and calcium copper titanate ($\text{CaCu}_3\text{Ti}_4\text{O}_{12}$ /CCTO) are key materials that are widely used in electrical applications⁽²⁻⁵⁾. Although significant progress has been made in developing these dielectric materials, the main challenges still include low energy storage density and high electron loss.

The substrate, known as a photocatalyst, is an essential component of the photocatalysis process, which uses light to speed up chemical reactions and remove pollutants

from the environment⁽⁶⁾. The nano-catalyst derived from calcium copper titanate, obtained from mineral industry waste, has shown promising results in reducing pollution problems and increasing energy efficiency⁽⁷⁾. Its ability to efficiently adsorb a wide range of contaminants, such as heavy metal ions, dyes, and organic molecules, makes calcium copper titanate an effective and versatile tool for water pollutant removal. Growing populations and accelerated industrialization have pushed scientists to look for green solutions to the pollution problem that use renewable energy sources like visible light. Pollutants and pharmaceutical waste can only decompose when exposed to UV light, which shares very small of its wavelengths with visible light⁽⁸⁾. TiO_2 is well known photo-catalytic in UV radiation and it belongs to the family of perovskite ABO_3 structure. CCTO perovskite shows good photo-catalytic performance in water pollutants and pharmaceutical waste. Photo-catalysis has gained a lot of interest due to its lower cost, increased capacity, and environmentally safe and green methods⁽⁹⁾. In the present study, the doping of metal transition Cobalt (Co) atoms in pure CCTO has been done to enhance its photo-catalytic properties.

In this study, the abbreviations CCTO and CCTCoO are used to refer to undoped $\text{CaCu}_3\text{Ti}_4\text{O}_{12}$ and $\text{CaCu}_3\text{Ti}_{4-x}\text{Co}_x\text{O}_{12}$ ($x = 0.05, 0.10, 0.15$), respectively. These materials were prepared using the solid-state reaction method. To determine their properties, X-ray diffraction (XRD), energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS), Field effect scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM), and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) were utilized to analyze their microstructure, size, and absorption bands.

2 Methodology

The raw materials CaCO_3 (Thomas Baker, purity>99%), CuO (Thomas Baker, AR grade), TiO_2 (Sigma Aldrich, purity>99.9%), and Co_3O_4 (Sigma Aldrich, purity>99.5%) were used for synthesis of pure ($\text{CaCu}_3\text{Ti}_4\text{O}_{12}$) and Co-doped calcium copper titanate ($\text{CaCu}_3\text{Ti}_{4-x}\text{Co}_x\text{O}_{12}$). Precursors are mixed by using an agate mortar. The mixture was then dried for 2 hours. Following this, the powder was calcined at 950°C for 12 hours in a programmable furnace with a heating rate of 4°C per minute.

To synthesize cobalt-doped CCTO ($\text{CaCu}_3\text{Ti}_{4-x}\text{Co}_x\text{O}_{12}$), we used cobalt oxide (Co_3O_4 , Sigma Aldrich, Purity>99.5%). Similarly, a solid-state reaction process was used to synthesize all of the cobalt-doped CCTO (CCTCoO), with varying doping concentrations of 5%, 10%, and 15%.

The XRD pattern of all precursors was confirmed by PANalytical X-ray Diffractometer (40kV, 30 mA). The pattern recorded with $\text{Cu-K}\alpha$ ($\lambda=1.54 \text{ \AA}$) in the 2θ range of 20° to 80° . FESEM is used to study the morphology and microstructure of CCTO. The study of chemical bonding has been done by using FT-IR spectroscopy.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 X-ray Diffraction

The XRD pattern of pure and cobalt-doped CCTO has been shown in Figure 1. The introduction of doped ions into the CCTO lattice is almost linked to the diffraction peak shift. The XRD pattern of 5% Co and 15% Co doped shows a distinct shift to lower angles of diffraction (220) peak, which is likely caused by the larger bivalent Co ionic radius⁽¹⁰⁾ which found that cobalt existing in +2 and +3 states can occupy Cu^{2+} and Ti^{4+} as separate, depending on its oxidation state. Based on the different ionic radius ($r(\text{Co}^{2+}) = 0.75 \text{ \AA}$, $r(\text{Co}^{3+}) = 0.55 \text{ \AA}$, $r(\text{Cu}^{2+}) = 0.57 \text{ \AA}$, and $r(\text{Ti}^{4+}) = 0.61 \text{ \AA}$), this is consistent with it. Ti ion substitution by a smaller trivalent Co ionic radius is the primary reason for the comparatively mild shift to higher angles in 10% doped CCTO. The lattice parameters were calculated to be 7.389, 7.409, 7.387, and 7.386 \AA , respectively. The variation in the lattice parameters shows good agreement with the shift tendency of the diffraction (220) peak that is due to the atomic radius differences. Research suggests that Co^{3+} ions are more suitable for occupying Ti sites than Cu sites in CCTO⁽¹¹⁾. The CCTO structure was confirmed using X-ray diffraction (XRD, PAN analytical) with $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$).

The size of the crystallites in the samples appears to decrease with an increase in the amount of Co doping. Figure 2 shows the crystallite size from the W-H plot, Debye-Scherrer, and Modified Scherrer equation. It is also essential to acknowledge that other factors, such as sample preparation and processing techniques, may also affect the properties of material.

Table 1. Lattice parameter of pure and Co doped samples

S.No.	Sample name	Lattice parameter (Å)
1.	CaCu ₃ Ti ₄ O ₁₂	7.389
2.	CaCu ₃ Ti _{3.95} Co _{0.05} O ₁₂	7.3892
3.	CaCu ₃ Ti _{3.90} Co _{0.10} O ₁₂	7.3878
4.	CaCu ₃ Ti _{3.85} Co _{0.15} O ₁₂	7.3894

Fig 1. XRD pattern of pure CCTO and co-doped CCTO at x= 5%, 10%, and 15%

Table 2. Crystallite size, micro-strain, and dislocation density by Williamson-Hall plot

Samples	Calcination (°C)	Williamson Hall plot size (in nm)	Dislocation Density (δ)	Debye-Scherrer equation size (in nm)	Modified Scherrer equation size (in nm)
CaCu ₃ Ti ₄ O ₁₂	950°C	48.1117608	0.043201368	31.5103124	37.11315371
CaCu ₃ Ti _{3.95} Co _{0.05} O ₁₂		30.17008333	0.109861868	24.30685709	26.76865074
CaCu ₃ Ti _{3.90} Co _{0.10} O ₁₂		15.47183761	0.417749754	15.67114674	15.35439042
CaCu ₃ Ti _{3.85} Co _{0.15} O ₁₂		44.28636086	0.050987065	31.15267611	35.88902198

3.2 FE-SEM (Field Effect Scanning Electron Microscopy Analysis)

The FE-SEM images of pure and Co-doped calcium copper titanate have been shown in Figure 2. The grains of the material are uniformly formed, with an average size of 1.0-1.3 micrometers, although smaller grains measuring 0.4-0.6 micrometers are present⁽¹²⁾. Interestingly, the cubic shape of the material remains unchanged even when cobalt is doped at various concentrations. This suggests that the doping process does not significantly affect the overall shape of the material. For instance, increasing the concentration of cobalt by 10% could potentially result in a more pronounced change in the shape of the material⁽¹³⁾. In the cobalt doping, it is seen that the average grain size of the sample lies between 0.3-0.5 μm. The smaller grain has to be found about 200 nm in the doping of 15% cobalt. The 15% has been shown lesser grain size as compared to other doping concentrations.

Fig 2. FE-SEM images of (a) pure CCTO and Co-doped (b) 5%, (c) 10%, (d) 15% CCTO

3.3 EDS (Energy Dispersive Spectra)

EDS gives the stoichiometric number of used precursors. EDS analysis is commonly utilized to examine the presence of elements in CCTO and to determine the weight percent of each element. Additionally, this technique reveals the varying concentrations of Co doping in both pure CCTO and the doped ceramics. When conducting EDS analysis, multiple regions of both pure and doped ceramics are focused and the results are displayed in Figure 3. In the same manner weight % of each element is seen for all samples. The presence of the carbon element is evident due to the sample being deposited on a carbon tape, resulting in a negligible weight for this element. The EDS spectra provide information on the Ca, Cu, and Ti elements in the pure ceramic and the weight percent of Co with Ca, Cu, and Ti in the doped samples⁽¹⁴⁾. The weights of Ca, Cu, and Ti were 6.15, 24.63, and 62.55, respectively for pure CCTO, while the atomic percentages were also provided for all elements in the synthesized powder samples. The EDS observations partially support the idea of Co replacing Ti at specific sites. The smallest grain size and thinnest intergranular phase, which may be related to the dielectric and electrical properties, are processed by 5% Co-doped CCTO. It is concluded that the co-doping causes a change in the grain size and the geometric form of the intergranular phase (related to the mechanical properties of the material).

3.4 FTIR Spectroscopy

Figure 4 shows the FT-IR spectra of all the synthesized samples. The Ti-O-Ti peak present at 460cm^{-1} wave number is indicative of strong chemical bonding between titanium and oxygen atoms in the material. This bond is a characteristic feature of titanium oxide and is responsible for its optical and electronic properties. This strong chemical bonding is likely due to the synthesis process of material at high temperatures, which promotes the formation of a TiO_6 crystalline structure. The peak at 570cm^{-1} corresponds to the vibrations of the Co-O bond, confirming the successful incorporation of cobalt ions into the calcium-copper titanate crystal structure. The intensity of this peak increased with increased cobalt concentration, suggesting that more cobalt ions are being incorporated into the lattice⁽¹⁵⁾. Additionally, the broadening of this peak suggests an increase in disorder and distortion of the crystal structure due to the substitution of larger cobalt ions for smaller titanium ions⁽¹⁶⁾. The presence of the 620cm^{-1} peak indicates the vibration of Cu-O bonds, which can be attributed to the copper oxide component in the material. The FTIR data provides evidence of the successful doping of cobalt into the calcium copper titanate structure and the formation of the desired crystal phases.

The CCTO structure displays the TiO_6 absorption band within the $380\text{-}700\text{cm}^{-1}$ range. The O-H bond peaks shift leftward, indicating enhanced bond stability⁽¹⁷⁾. The peak shifting indicates energy storage applications. The large absorption band gives the enhancement of photocatalytic activity. Co-doping CCTO with 10% Co increases stability and, thereby can be used for the photocatalytic activity of CCTO. Additionally, the small size of CCTO nanoparticles enhances their efficiency in degrading organic compounds under UV light. This will help in the field of pharmaceutical waste management and water pollutants^(18,19).

Fig 3. EDS images of (a) pure CCTO and Co-doped (b) 5%, (c) 10%, (d) 15% CCTO

Fig 4. FTIR spectra of Pure and Co-doped CCTO

4 Conclusion

Pure and Co-doped samples were prepared by the solid-state reaction method to provide structural information about the samples. The XRD patterns of all the samples clearly show that the peaks are shifted towards a lower angle. The crystal structure was decreased by the doping of Co atom due to the difference in ionic radii of Co and Ti. FESEM gives smaller grain sizes of up to 0.3-0.5 μm . The particle size is about 200 nm by the doping of 15% Co. FT-IR analysis shows the stretching of the O-H bond towards a lower wave number. Therefore, it is used for energy storage applications. This will enhance the photocatalytic activity of the samples. In future applications, Co-doped CCTO can be used as organic compounds under UV light and have significant implications for various industries such as pharmaceuticals and environmental remediation of water pollutants.

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